

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A531

2 April 1997

OXICOA

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 531

DATE: 02 104 197

Take off: 12 55 Z

Landing: 15 55 Z

Aircraft Scientist : A HAYE
Flight Leader : D PERCIVAL
Others : H RICHER
K DEWEY
J HENT
D TIDDEMAN
B BANDY
S BAUGHITTLE
T GREEN
G MILLS

Captain : SQN LDR C O'BRIEN
Co-pilot : FLT LT M PURSE
Navigator : FLT LT J CANNING
Engineer : MENG N NEWTON
Loadmaster : MENG K QUICK

Trials Instructions ACSOE :
Operating area : SOUTHWEST / SCILLYS.

General synoptic situation

TIME: 12

2/4/97

Sortie Brief: ACSOE - Azores Instrument Test Flight

SF26: Stephane Bauguitte

Sortie Objective: To test all chemical instrumentation.

Operational Area: To be chosen by air crew.

Weather conditions: Avoid areas of cloud and precipitation.

Flight Pattern:

1. Depart Boscombe Down (12:00 local) maintaining altitude at 3000ft until wet chemistry instruments are checked.
2. Profile ascent to 5000ft maintain horizontal run until wet chemistry instruments are checked.
3. Continue profile ascent to FL150 and maintain horizontal run for 20 minutes.
4. Transit and descend into operational area (if time allows).
5. Fifteen minutes in boundary layer for instrument calibration (if time allows).
6. Ascend to maximum safe altitude, maintain for 15 minutes.
7. Descend to FL150 maintain horizontal run for 15 minutes.
8. Descend into Boscombe Down, arriving at 16:00 local.

Other requirements:

Constant pressurisation on horizontal runs.

Profiles to be carried out at 1000 ft/minute above the boundary layer, 500 ft/minute below the boundary layer.

A531 02-APR-97 12:55:35-15:53:15GMT

A531 02-APR-97 Height time series

AIRCRAFT FLYING PROGRAMME

DATE 2 April 1997

FLIGHT NO A531

FTI MRF01 ACSOE- Azores shake-down

Aircraft scientist H Richer / A Kaye

Flight leader D Percival

Cloud physics ~~M Pickering~~

Chemistry K Dewey / J Kent / D Tiddeman / B Bandy /

S Bauguitte / T Green / G Mills

Pre-flight clearance D Findley / D Arthur dep 0800 + S HEATH

FTOs Depart F'boro 0900

Briefing 1000 Take off 1200 Return 1600

Press RETURN for next display (H for help)

NEXT DAY 1-APR-1997 10:15

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:02:33		Flow 1	3000	P	266	51.07	-2.29	10 minute delay because of flow problems. Very hazy ahead. Some cu ahead in haze.	
13:09								into heavy cloud Cu & hazy below.	
13:10:09		^{R1} P1	3000	P	266	51.05	-2.08	climb to F1150 4200 /13:12 out of cloud. Sc below clear above.	
13:13:45	07	P1 P1	FL 1500 FL 1500	P	266	51.04	-3.16	clear above sc below.	
13:22:38	08	R2/ P2	450	FL	266	50.99	-3.77	clear above 7/8 sc below	
13:28:57		P2	117	FL	266	50.95	-4.33	clear above & below but 8/8 8/8 sc ahead.	
13:32:19	09	P2 R3	150	FL	265	50.94	-4.61	clear above 8/8 sc below. 13:34:20 Press	
13:52:40	10	R3/ P3	150	FL	265	50.86	-6.38	clear above 8/8 sc below.	
13:54:21	11	P3	150	FL	170	50.76	-6.33	7/8 sc below ^{some banding} some gaps to SBRED. clear above. 50-51 1018 6 w/in.	
13:58:05		P3	4000	P	184	50.17	-6.31	8/8 sc below. Silly Isles visible ahead in gap in cloud.	
								500 ft/min @ 1500 ft	
14:08:39								interrupt flow to get clear of land @ 800 ft.	

ZZ

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	INS Heading	Omeg Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
					Latitude	Longitude		
14:10:03	15	P3	800	353	50.06	-6.40	Sc below 500ft cloud tops.	
14:11:20	17	R4	800	354	50.13	-6.46	Sc 7/8 below could not finish profile. because of low cloud OAH 1020 & Sea state 2 slight small climb to keep clear of cloud.	
14:25:25	18	R4	1100	3	50.90	-6.46	Sc below clear above.	
14:27:44	19	P4	1100	166	50.88	-6.41	Fl 20600/14:46:00 Perovids: channel lead. continuing climb	
14:47:30		P4	FL246	344	50.45	-5.89	Sc below, some banding visible clear above.	
14:53:37	20	P4	F270	354	50.81	-5.95	4/8 Sc Below clear above	
14:54:06	21	R5	FL270	69	50.89	-5.02		
15:11:50	22	R5e	FL270		51.38	-3.73	4/8 on below Sc to SBRD clear above.	
15:13:11	23	P5	FL270	255	51.33	-3.78	large sheets of sc ahead clear above.	
15:25:06	24	P5/R6	FL150	91	51.13	-4.27	2/8 on below Heavy, clear above.	

155

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A531

Date: 040297

A/S Name: TAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for ...4.....

2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period

3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project ...ACSOE.....

4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long?10 YRS.....

5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?

6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?

7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A531 Date: 0204 97 User: KATE
Interactive by: D PERCIVAL
Date: 0304 97

Renav

Kalman Filtering Used.

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = -

b = +

c = + Not Fitted.

LWC

NO PMS DATA AS NOT FITTED

OK.

Heimann / Barnes

OK

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A531

Date: 020497

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1021	REF +	5	0567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2856	/		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	0087	F/S O/S	TORQUE 3.5	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	2106	F/S O/S	TORQUE 3.0	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0000	/		As Indicated	0000
	PR HT	8	3874	1000	1007	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3244	NOISEY			
	A/S	9	0082	/		As ASI	0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	1647	530	534		
	UP2S	82	1465	260	293		
	UIRS	83	0574	- 287	1558		
	UP1Z	84	152	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	147	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	584	x		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2444	19	16	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2430	19		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0200	133 ?		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	235	32	33		
	LP2S	92	192	278 13	155 10		
	LIRS	93	0065	- 400	1558		
	LP1Z	94	151	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	154	/		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	66	/		Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2521	15		As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2487	17		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0000			As IAT	
	J/W	42	0897	/		As Indicated	0000
	HYGR	58	2728	8	8.1		
	HYCC	59	726	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1741	-10	9.5	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	0608				
	DTF	10	564	16	/		
	DTC	11	6	8			
	NDTF	23	4045			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	7				
	INCT	48	2392				
	HEIM	141	2480				
	PRTC	142	2381	/		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	4095			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	4095			0640-1860	< min
	O3	100	139				
	O3P	106	2030	957		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1421				
1044							

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1050	FL NO	1	Hex	0531	/		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0105	105012	/	Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0012			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	2-73	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3569 19	1500 3855	3569	SD	3569	3704	3569	0136.
	LATC	160	Dec	4094			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4094.			Longitude
1053.							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72				0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76				0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77				0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	☐ Off ☒ On	Large/ ☒ Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	☐ Off ☒ On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1346	FL NO	1	Hex	531	/		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0134			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0634	/		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0009	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
242.0 -9.3	1292 3255	2430	1321	2430	3729	2431	0172
	LATC	160	Dec	0578	50.864° W		Latitude
	LONG	161	Dec	4027	352 -5.624 W		Longitude
1349							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72				0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76				0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77				0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's ~~218~~/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: 4531

Date: 020497

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1306	REF +	5	0567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2856	/		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	1482	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1246	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	2766	3300	3300 /	As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3474	3.3	3.2	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3414	1030			
	A/S	9	1300	178	180	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	2033	672	693		
	UP2S	82	1736	318	341		
JN02	UIRS	83	0909	-220	1558		
	UP1Z	84	151	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	145	/		Approx 0149	
JN02	UIRZ	86	0844			Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2638	10	5.6	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2655	9		As IAT	
1323	UIRT	89	0000			As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0600	181	191		
	LP2S	92	0609	116	134		
JN02	LIRS	93	456	-320	1558		
	LP1Z	94	151	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	157	/		Approx 0146	
JN02	LIRZ	96	311	/		Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2804	3	-6.4	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2807	3	-7.4	As IAT	
JN02	LIRT	99	0000			As IAT	
	J/W	42	1152	0.1		As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	1613	-27	-28		
	HYCC	59	221			696-901	
	FDEW	138	1656	-17.2	-2.1	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	608				
	DTF	10	2586	-8			
	DTC	11	4				
	NDTF	23	4095			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	0007				
	INCT	48	2615				
	HEIM	141	2223				
	PRTC	142	2379	/		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	4095			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	4095			0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0185				
	O3P	106	1487	939.8		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	2101				
1334							

Flight Leader's ~~Pre~~/In-Flight Check List

W. Law

Flight No: #531

Date: 02 04 97

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1400	REF +	5	0567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2856	/		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	1724	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1263	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4045	FL 060	/	As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3133	5.8	/	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3450	1050			
	A/S	9	1335	120	/	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	1931	635	637		
	UP2S	82	1513	275	323		
3002	UIRS	83	791	-244	1558		
	UP1Z	84	150	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	146	/		Approx 0149	
3002	UIRZ	86	781			Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2596	12	6.4	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2616	12		As IAT	
3002	UIRT	89	0000			As IAT	
	LP1S	91	715	228	264		
	LP2S	92	558	105	121		
3002	LIRS	93	427	-320	1558		
	LP1Z	94	151	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	158	/		Approx 0146	
3002	LIRZ	96	379	/		Approx 2050	
3002	LP1T	97	2826	-1	-8.3	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2832	-1		As IAT	
3002	LIRT	99	0000			As IAT	
4006	J/W	42	1176	0-0		As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	1577	-28	-26		
	HYCC	59	0729	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	938	-53.1		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	965				
	DTF	10	1640	-11			
	DTC	11	4				
	NDTF	23	4045	/		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	0007				
	INCT	48	2492				
	HEIM	141	2140				
	PRTC	142	2379	/		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	4045	/		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	4045	/		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	136				
	O3P	106	1637	799.8		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1977				
1444							

Flight Leaders' ~~Pre~~/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1500	FL NO	1	Hex	0531	/		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0150	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0024	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0021	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
-33 1446	1260 3855	1444	2372	1463	3821	1439	0172 /
	LATC	160	Dec	0581	51.12 N	✓	Latitude
	LONG	161	Dec	4040	4.48 W	/	Longitude
1504							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72				0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76				0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77				0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

603 P1
MP P2
30 V
NN E
KE LM

Flight No A 531..... Date 020497..... Page 1 of 2

Video Tape
No. A531 #1
Ends 1600
FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	51° 09.83N	51° 09.83 N
Long	1° 44.61W	01° 44.60W
Time	10:12	101700
Status	OK	GC ALIGN

DRS recording to HORACE n
HORACE recording to disc n
SATCOM sending pos. reports n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
100435				DATA ON					
				Power set tripped when switched on	Air Pump.				
201218	123005			SET TO NAV.					
125535				TAKE OFF BOSCOMBE DOWN					
1258		3000	1006	Level 3000 ft. RUN 1	180	4.0	1.2	OFF	264/13
1304				Heiman Cal POS					
31016	6	3000	1006	End Run 1 Start P1.	180	2.0	2.0	OFF	500 RPM 302/6
31345	7	FL050	1013	END P1 // START RUN 2.	180	5.5	0.8	OFF	298/13
				Heiman Cal POS					
132232	8	FL050	1013	END RUN 2 // START P 2	180	5.7	-2.3	OFF	1000 RPM 294/12
33220	9	FL150	1013	END P 2 // START RUN 3	180	-13.4	-2.1	OFF	263/13
135216	10	FL150	1013	END RUN 3 // START P 3	180	-13	-2.8	OFF	269/15
135421	11	FL150	1013	START P 3	180	-13.0	-2.7	OFF	500 RPM 270/17

Video Tape
 No. A 531
 Ends 1600
 FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	50° 37.75 _N	50 35.00 _N
Long	086° 19.08 _W	6 19 53 _W
Time	1356 29	13 57 18
Status	CR	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE y/n
 HORACE recording to disc y/n
 SATCOM sending pos reports y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
		2000			P3	changed to		500 FPM	
140449	12	FL090	1013	290	180	6.0	9.5	OFF	279/9
140643	13					7.3	-2.6		...
		INT	END	P3					
140837	14	500 200	1013	290	180	8.6	3.6	OFF	236/04
			Restart	P3					500 FPM
141006	15	800 ^{FT}	1013	360	180	8.6	6.1	OFF	
			END	P3					
141058	16	500 ^{FT}	1020						3522
			START	Run 4					
141124	17	800 ^{FT}	1020	360	180	8.4	6.5	OFF	230/5
1420			came up to	avoid	cloud.				
			END	Run 4					
142620	18	9100	1020	360	180	7.7	5.4	OFF	228/9
			START	P 4	↗				
142711	19	1100	1020	175	180	7.0	1.1	OFF	254/12
			END	P 4	P				
145332	20	FL270	1013	350	160	-39.9	-52.1	OFF	288/13
			START	Run 5					
145507	21	FL270	1013	080	180	-39.9	-52.9	OFF	265/14
			END	Run 5					
151156	22	FL270	1013	080	180	-41	-53	OFF	20/18

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

01223
336518
6473 FAX

Kathy @ ATM.CH-CAM.AC.UH

Flight No A 531.....

Date 0204 97.....

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617/618

Video Tape	
No. A 531 # 1	
inds 1600	
(FC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	51° 17.43N	51° 17.31
Long	3° 51.81W	3° 54.23W
Time	1514	1515
Status	OK	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	(y/n)
HORACE recording to disc	(y/n)
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y/n)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				START	P 5	7			
51304	23	FL270	1013	260	180	363	-52	1000/mi OFF	272/15
				END	P 5	7	START	R6	
72507	24	FL150	1013	095	180	-13.6	-35.8	OFF	262/15
				END	R6				
4150	25	FL150	1013	100	180	-13.8	-30.4	OFF	258/16
55315				LAND	BOXCOM BE				
55403				HOLD	RT				
						51 09	85		
						1 44	63		
163753				DATA	OFF				

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No A 531

Project ACSOE

Date 02 04 97

Tape No A531 User KAYE

Retention Period 10 Yrs

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
1300	0	FFC	Run 1 3000 ^{ft}
131016 - 131345			P1 3000 ^{ft} - FL050
131345 - 132232			Run 2 FL050
132232 133220			P2 FL050 - FL150
132220 135216			R3 FL150
135421 141058			P3 FL150 - 500 ^{ft}
141124 - 142620			Run 4 800 ^{ft}
142711 - 145332			P4 1100 ^{ft} - FL270
145507 - 151156			Run 5 FL270
151304 - 152507			P5 FL270 - FL150.
152507 - 154150			Run 6 FL150.
1600			End Tape.

pressure parameter = 419

PAN GC Log

1 meet time = 405

no humidifier

ONLY TWO ac' RESPONDING (B-C)

WIN
FOR CORE

GC Sample record			Flight Number: AS31					Operator: RICHER / KENT										Date: 2/4/97			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1 (A)					Channel 2 (B)					Channel 3 (C)					Comments			
			Optimisation =					Optimisation =					Optimisation =								
			ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	FR	ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	FR	ST	SP	DT		DP	BT	FR
							25.88							24.87						24.28	PREFLIGHT
1	13:01	3000ft																			✓ GAGER ON ✓ AUTO ON
2	13:07		315.35	2100	35.1	1505	20.4		317.65	1569	29.7	262	00.4		317.75	2377	27.5	127	00	NO SAMPLE	
3	13:16:22	5000ft	315.35	2008					318.00	2356					314.31	2206					PEAKS VOLTS OF AUTO SCALE?
4	13:24:18	FL450	315.55	2323	35.9	689	21.4		318.51	2507	29.8	1200			315.3	2346	26.5	213		BASELINE OF CABIN PRESSURE =	
5	13:34:34	FL150	315.40	2377	36.0	1451	31.1				29.8	1206					27.4	1210			
6	13:50:13	FL150	315.40	2377					314.35	1915					315.70	1908					- SAMPLE TOO LATE FOR RUN (END OF RUN)
7	14:11:52	7000ft	315.15	2762	35.8	1512	30.8		318.40	2457	29.7	1271			315.05	2300	27.4	1280			
8	14:20:13	7000ft	315.25	2737	35.4	1512	30.7		314.8	2468	29.7	1271			315.05	2312	27.7	1287		(SAMPLE RATHER LATE - REPEAT END OF RUN LARGE PEAK)	
9	14:55:02	FL270	315.25	1521	35.8	1277	20.5		314.44	1322	29.8	1004			315.5	1187	27.4	1006			
10	15:03:20	FL270	315.20	1528	35.7	1266	20.1		318.25	1336	29.8	989			315.15	1336	27.3	992		"	
11	15:26:06	FL150	315.00	2088	35.3	1443	28.6		317.25	1176	29.5	1187			313.35	1147	27.1	1199		LOTS OF NOISE	
12	15:35:10	FL150	315.05	2069	35.0	1439	28.5		316.78	1183	29.5	1184			313.35	1047	27.0	1195		"	
13	16:10	GROOND	315.2																		
14	16:21:01	GROOND	315.25	2814					315.45	2577					337.11	2427					

IGNORE FIRST SAMPLE

PEAKS VOLTS OF AUTO SCALE? BASELINE OF CABIN PRESSURE =

- SAMPLE TOO LATE FOR RUN (END OF RUN) (SAMPLE RATHER LATE - REPEAT END OF RUN LARGE PEAK)

AIRCRA SPEED = 225 knt

BF 28.10

BF 20.5

BF 31.13

(Bubble flow meter)

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: 531 Date: 2/4/97 Page: 1 / 2
 Campaign: ACSOE/OXICOA Operator(s): Green/Baugnitte
 Take-Off Time: N 1255 Can Flush Off: 1257

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
1302	3300	end of		ARTIFACT			→ AMBIENT AIR	
130620	3300	ZERO	460	2300	1300	1000	1st zero (sequenced)	
1310							start of profile P1	P1
131345	5000						end of P1	P1
NB	put ZA values on manual for out-of-flight artifact -							
	1st calibration (for NO only GPT all shutters not adjusted)							
133220	15000						end of P2 start of R3	
1333	ZERO	450	?					
1333	15000	ZERO	450	2350	1250	1000	sequenced	
133650	15000	CAL	87000	97000			NO & NO2 detectors	
133750	15000	CAL			100000	80000	NOy1 & NOy2 detectors	
1347	15000	ZERO	950	2300			on NO & NO2 w. cal on	
1348	15000	ZERO	1750	2000	1750	900	on NOys (off on NO2)	
1349	15000	ZERO	OFF					
1350	15000	CAL	OFF					
1352	going down	to 50'					end of Run 3	
141220	700	ZERO	310	1900	1000	650	sequenced	
1424	700	ZERO	300	1800	900	580	not sequenced	
142550	700	ZERO	off					
142620							end of R4	
142711	↑						start of profile to Max Rt P4	
1446 ^R	20.5 kft						NO2 Raw still low @ 15.0 PM NO2 cell P. still holding @ 280 torr	
1447	22 kft						NO2 cell Pres dropping	
1449	23.5 kft						~250 torr (NO2 cell P2)	
1450	24.5						~230 torr	
145338	27 kft						end of P4	
145507	27 kft						start of R5	
↓ NO2	Pres. control valve	critic adjusted					→ 244 torr (Max. Press. achieved)	
1508	27	ZERO	550	2200	1150	820	Scavenged	

Note: All times logged as GMT

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: 531

Date: 2/4/97

Page: 212

Campaign: ACSCE/UXICOA

Operator(s): Green/Saugnette

Take-Off Time: 1255

Can Flush Off: 1257

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
1513	27kft ↓						start of P5	
							NO ₂ cell Press. increasing → 1	
1515	25kft						tropopause crossed → increase on all 4 channels	
1518	22kft						NO ₂ cell Press. @ 300 torr	
1525	15kft						NO ₂ cell Press. @ ~415 torr	
1530	15kft						NO ₂ cell Press. control a def P5 & start of P7	
							value back @ ~280 torr	
1531	15000	CAL	81000	100000	91200	7800	shutter off - NO cal on 4 channels	
							NB - NO & NO ₂ signals undulations observed again	
1540	15000	ZERO	900	2100	1570	710	not sequenced.	
1541	15000	ZERO	OFF					
1542	15000	CAL	OFF					
1544	↓	ARTIF.					sequenced.	
1548	ph						NO ₂ cell Press. at 600 @ 600 torr	
1550							can flush on	
							need to readjust on gas!	

Note: All times logged as GMT

FORMALDEHYDE INSTRUMENT LOG SHEET

Date: 2/4/77 Flight No. ^{A 531} ~~7237 A7~~ Operator: GRHAM Page: 1 of 1
 Air Sampling Rate: 1.54 ~~6.00~~ ^{320 ~ actual} Peristaltic Pump Speed (rpm): 3 PMT Sensitivity: 30
 Calib Factor (V to ppt): 1 mV = 7.5 ppt Approx Lag Time: 5 mins React Coil Temp: 91°C
 _____ drs Bits = 1V

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other info/Remarks e.g altitude, lamp output, Sampling rate changes etc.
			Pre Flight
09:18:50	2	0.75	Restarted after power down. Lamp = 7.26V debubbler a bit erratic. 10/17 Min Zero in <u>Control</u>
09:21:51	A	0.74	Started outside sampling.
09:23	A	0.73/7	
09:24:24	A	0.76/1	
09:26:21	A	0.75	response time = ~ <u>14:30</u>
09:29:50	A	0.96	
09:29:30	A	0.98	
09:41:00	2	0.73	
09:44:07	2	0.72	
09:45:00	A	0.73	} changed zero to 10 mins/Amb 10 mins
09:50:30	A	0.87	
09:50:30	A	0.87	
9:53:30	A	0.98	
10:00:15h	-	-	TEST All Power.
10:02	-	-	Restarted System - Ambient Sample.
10:04:50	2	1.28	STARTED 20 Min Zero after ~ 2/3 mins ambient sampling after restart. Lamp = 7.23 V.
10:21	2	1.64	Set zero to 8 mins. / start. zero
10:26:00	2	-7	Starting to go down
10:30:00	A	0.72	
10:32:00	A	0.71	
10:35:05	2	1.35	Started 6 Minute <u>zero</u>
10:39:43	2	1.64	
10:44:30	A	0.73	not quite long enough zero Set to 6:30
10:52:30	2	1.45	Started 6:30 zero.

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A 531

Date: 2/4/97

Page: 2 / 17

Campaign: Acidic (700-16) Operator(s): CLANAN MULLS

Air Sampling Rate: 1.545 L/min Peristaltic Pump Speed: 3 (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: 30 Calib Factor: 1.0 ^{7.5 ppt} (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: 4:50 React Coil Temp: 91°C

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
12:15:00	—	—	powered down + Pump isolation
			FOR POWER TRANSFER
12:58:06	Z	0.87	take ^{12:55:17} off + started zero cycle.
13:01:37	Z	300+	set from pump to 7.00 to help
			deur solus.
13:03	Z	.95	Returned to 3.00 RPM.
13:07:18	Z	0.63V	—
13:07:30	Z	—	went into cloud.
13:07:30	Z	—	—
13:07:30	Z	0.70	—
13:10:09	A	0.70	climbing @ 500' per min incl started ambient sample
			—
13:14:30	A	0.71	5000 feet. 5000
13:15:30	A	0.75	some structure during climb
13:17:00	A	0.80	SYSTEM WORKING OK
			Some structure seen during climb.
13:18:55	A	0.80	—
13:22:00	A	—	Start Probe (2) to FL150 @ 1000 LPM
13:29:06	A	0.78	climbing still
13:30:00	A	0.73	"
13:32:20	Z	0.74	Start Run (3) - Started zero @ FL150
13:36:41	Z	0.75	Temp = 88.9°C
13:39:27	Z	0.71	Pump samples @ 0.85 L/min
13:43:06	A	0.68	started ambient sample - ^{END} zero
			Sample Rate = 0.925 L/min
13:47:00	A	0.67	—

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A 531

Date: 2/6/97

Page: 3 / 14

Campaign: _____ Operator(s): _____

Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
13:50:20	A	0.71	FL 150 -
13:52:21			
13:56:21	A	0.67	Start Profile (3) from FL 150
			boundary 175
14:07:45	A	0.70	inside boundary layer
14:08:30	A	0.70	interrupt profile @ 300'
14:10:00	A	-	no sig - profile - run 800'
14:11:02	A		end profile (3) return to 800'
14:11:30	Z	-	Started zero @ 800' run (4)
14:18:30	Z	0.68	
14:20:14	Z	0.68	END zero started Amb. Sample
14:26:20	A		end of run (4) starting climb
14:27:11	A	0.73	} Profile A to 27000' } Sample @ 1.56 SLM
14:32:50	A	0.78	Flow = 1.38 SLM
14:56:30	A	0.73	Flow = 1.21 SLM
14:37:30	A	0.71	Flow = 1.10 ~ 12000'
14:37:30			
14:39:30	A	0.71	Flow = 1.00 SLM
14:47-	A	0.69	Flow = 0.87 SLM ~ 1170
14:45:30		0.67	Flow = 0.75 SLM ~ 20000
14:49:40	A	0.69	Flow = 0.60
14:53:-	Z	0.67	started zero - started run = 0.67 and profile (5)
14:55:07	Z	0.70	Start run (5) at FL 27000 Temp = 85°C - There is a few flow probs in de-bubbler

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A 531 Date: 2/6/97 Page: 1/14
 Campaign: _____ Operator(s): _____
 Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)
 PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V
 Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
15:01:00	Z	0.65	- zero a bit noisy at this altitude.
15:02:30			de-bubbler caused working.
15:06:57	A	0.79	de-bubbler fixed. Working ok again. Flow = 0.51
15:11:06	A		End of run (5) - descending.
15:12:56	A	0.71	
15:13:00	A		Start profile (5) from FL 270
15:15:52	A	0.69	Flow = 0.58
15:18:14	A	0.67	blip 27600' - 0.3002 pressure approx. here Flow = 0.67 SLM
15:21:06	A	0.67	Flow = 0.75 - Fl 190 ± descending
15:24:00	A	0.63	Flow = 0.70
15:25:07			End profile (5) now @ Fl 150
15:25:30	Z	0.68	START 7600 ZERO START Run (6) Flow = 0.80 L (low - then about because of chemical filter)
15:38:00	Z	0.68	lamp = 718. Flow = 0.80
15:36:08	A	0.67	End Zero - Start ambient sample.
15:38:00	A	0.66	Air Sample rate = 0.91
15:41:50	A	0.66	End of run (6)

DATE 2 APR 97 TI MRF 01 NAV CANNING

AIRFIELD BD AIRFIELD BD 1

R/W 23 W/V 270/05 TEMP +15 ONH 1020 OFF 1006 R/W 23 W/V 260/8 TEMP +15 ONH 1018 OFF 1003

WX F/S BLU REF 1018 10K 3/3500 WX J BLUE SK 2/3800

ATC CL F150 ATC CL

T/O TIME 1255 LAND TIME 0555 3:00

TIME	HGD	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
13 ¹⁶	267	3P	169	180	193	37/18	F50		N51023 W03557	P1
13 ⁴⁵	265	4P	175	184	200	29/24	F50		N51018 W03075	P2
22 ³⁸	267	4P	170	182	202	21/22	F150		N50585 W03473	P2
32 ²⁰	267	1S	178	182	222	25/24	F150		N50562 W04350	R3
52 ¹⁶							—		N50510 W06202	—
54 ²¹	180	7P	228	183	228	21/32	F150		N50547 W06208	P3
1408 ⁵⁷							800		N49591 W06224	—
11 ²⁴	353	2S	170	180	180	23/08	800		N50064 W0628.3	P4
26 ²⁰									N50520 W06275	—
27 ¹¹	167	6P	181	182	185	24/20	800		N50522 W06247	P4
53 ³⁸									N50471 W05554	—
55 ⁰⁷	070	1S	290	170	270	26/20	F270		N50516 W05470	R5
1511 ⁵⁶									N51217 W03450	—
23 ⁴⁴	256	2P	237	185	225	24/30	→		N51189 W03430	P5
2507	091	2P	254	183	257	26/28	F150		N51056 W04175	R6
41 ⁵⁰									N51055 W02269	—

A531, 2nd April, 1997
ACSOE
Shake Down Flight

<u>Start time</u>	<u>End time</u>	<u>Event</u>	<u>Height(s)</u>	<u>Hdg</u>	<u>Comments</u>
125535					Take off from Boscombe
125800	131016	R1	3000'	270°	Instrument warm up run
131016	131345	P1	3000'-FL050	270°	500 feet per min
131345	132232	R2	FL050	270°	
132232	133220	P2	FL050-FL150	270°	1000 feet per minute
132220	135216	R3	FL150	270°	
135421	141058	P3	FL150- 500'	180°-290°	1000fpm to 2000'
141124	142620	R4	800'-1100'	360°	Climbed to avoid cloud.
142711	145338	P4	1100'-FL270	180°-360°	1000fpm
145507	151156	R5	FL270	080°	
151304	152507	P5	FL270-FL150	260°-095°	1000fpm
152507	154150	R6	FL150	100°	
155315					Land at Boscombe

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: A531

DATE: 02 / 04 / 97

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	/ / / /		
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP HEIMANN HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	/ / X / / / X / / / / / /		
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS SAFIRE DEIMOS ARIES	/ / 3NO2 / / 3NO2 X X X X		
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX Y	/ / /		
OTHERS: CCM CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER PSAP	X X / X X		

A531 02 APR 97 13:30:57 008 50.95 -4.47 AS P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg
267.	605.	13.6	222.	-10.8	-26.1	270/12

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A531 02-APR-97 13:40:45 009 Ω 50.91 -5.33 AS

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
266.	571.	15.0	223.	-13.4	-33.5	264/12

GE DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A531 02-APR-97 14:12:36 017 Ω 50.18 -6.42 AS P

HG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg/mph
354.	992.	0.6	181.	8.2	6.4	231/5

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A531 02-APR-97 14:58:33 021 50.99 -5.40 AS P

HDT deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg
66.	346.	26.9	275.	-40.1	-51.7	262/14

GE DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	.PARAS	FREQ	700M			VTDF0	HEIP

01 00Z WED 2/ 4/97 VT 00Z WED 2/ 4/97 GMAIN I+ 0 HEIGHT DM. 300MB

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.25.58 CHART 27 PHDA30 EGRR 0000Z

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:55:30 CHART 27 PHDE30 EGRR 0000Z

FACTIT 4-UP
02 APR '97 13:40

12Z 02 APR 1997

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_4 PAGE. 001

10	275	72
15	275	90
20	275	88
25	270	101
30	260	93
40	260	80
50	260	74
60	265	62
70	265	50
85	250	45
100		

MAX 18867
205 105

TROP 234 -64
265 102

10	1585
15	1325
20	1144
25	1006
30	890
40	697
50	538
70	286
85	134
100	2

10	260.0
15	181.0
20	138.0
25	116.0
30	103.0
40	159.0
50	251.8
60	284.5
70	131.9
85	536.3

10	-55
15	-55
20	-61

10	290	29
15	285	23
20	290	23
25	320	12
30	310	10
40	280	12
50	295	12
60	275	12
70	255	4
85	245	4
100	255	6

MAX NIL

TROP 229 -59
315 16

10	1615
15	1357
20	1174
25	1034
30	917
40	722
50	563
70	305
85	150
100	17

10	258.0
15	185.0
20	140.0
25	117.0
30	103.0
40	159.0
50	257.6
60	288.0
70	132.4
85	545.6

10	-57
15	-55
20	-58

10	315	12
15	295	21
20	285	20
25	290	27
30	285	45
40	275	26
50	265	15
60	280	15
70	285	12
85	305	11
100	035	3

MAX NIL

TROP 219 -59
285 27

10	1620
15	1362
20	1180
25	1040
30	922
40	727
50	565
70	309
85	153
100	18

10	258.0
15	182.0
20	140.0
25	118.0
30	103.0
40	161.0
50	257.3
60	290.7
70	134.8
85	548.0

10	-56
15	-56
20	-58

10	290	29
15	285	23
20	290	23
25	320	12
30	310	10
40	280	12
50	295	12
60	275	12
70	255	4
85	245	4
100	255	6

MAX NIL

TROP 229 -59
315 16

10	1615
15	1357
20	1174
25	1034
30	917
40	722
50	563
70	305
85	150
100	17

10	258.0
15	185.0
20	140.0
25	117.0
30	103.0
40	159.0
50	257.6
60	288.0
70	132.4
85	545.6

10	-57
15	-55
20	-58

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
1 1	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
1 of 3 2 of 3 3 1	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log
1	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
1 1 1 1 1	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

A531 02-APR-97

P1 3000'-FL050(131016-131345) + P2 FL050-FL150(132232-133220)

A531 02-APR-97

P3 FL150-500'(135421-141058) + P4 1100'-FL270(142711-145338)

A531 02-APR-97

P5 FL270-FL150(151304-152507)

A531 02-APR-97 R1 3000' From 125800 - 131016 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:20

A531 02-APR-97 R1 3000' From 125800-131016 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:20

A531 02-APR-97 R1 3000' From 125800 - 131016 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 16:57

A531 02-APR-97 R1 3000' From 125800-131016 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 16:58

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 737
Mean 900.415
Standard dev 1.52309
Max value 903.879
Min value 896.797

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 737
Mean 276.511
Standard dev 0.490098
Max value 277.623
Min value 274.707

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 737
Mean 274.813
Standard dev 0.860523
Max value 277.214
Min value 271.905

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 737
Mean 54.9860
Standard dev 6.15933
Max value 63.8241
Min value 42.6112

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
No of obs 737
Mean 27.4947
Standard dev 21.3500
Max value 52.4834
Min value 3.87679

PEROXIDE (PPB)
No of obs 737
Mean 3.178290e-02
Standard dev 6.845338e-02
Max value 0.912000
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 737
Mean 929.656
Standard dev 57.5518
Max value 1047.67
Min value 787.846

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 737
Mean 51.0776
Standard dev 2.190052e-02
Max value 51.1155
Min value 51.0466

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 737
Mean -2.37480
Standard dev 0.277045
Max value -1.89619
Min value -2.85791

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 737
Mean 0.875776
Standard dev 2.11088
Max value 4.47255
Min value -4.67893

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 737
Mean 2.92899
Standard dev 0.721941
Max value 5.08736
Min value 0.730125

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 737
Mean 4.835214e-02
Standard dev 0.713172
Max value 3.77525
Min value -2.02316

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 737
Mean 3.68517
Standard dev 0.858307
Max value 5.75515
Min value 1.15004

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 253.353

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 737
Mean 95.6215
Standard dev 1.55214
Max value 99.9229
Min value 90.1457

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 263.520

A531 02-APR-97 P1 3000'-FL050 From 131016-131345 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:21

A531 02-APR-97 P1 3000'-FL050 From 131016-131345 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:21

A531 02-APR-97 P1 3000'-FL050 From 131016-131345 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 16:59

A531 02-APR-97 P1 3000'-FL050 From 131016-131345 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 16:59

A531 02-APR-97 R2 FL050 From 131345-132232 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:23

A531 02-APR-97 R2 FL050 From 131345-132232 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:23

A531 02-APR-97 R2 FL050 From 131345-132232 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:02

A531 02-APR-97 R2 FL050 From 131345-132232 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 842.813
 Standard dev 1.25072
 Max value 846.605
 Min value 840.498

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 278.559
 Standard dev 0.169249
 Max value 278.818
 Min value 278.105

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 272.165
 Standard dev 1.66074
 Max value 274.555
 Min value 269.368

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 52.0930
 Standard dev 2.77449
 Max value 58.8132
 Min value 46.1659

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 15.4839
 Standard dev 2.89477
 Max value 19.7023
 Min value 11.0199

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 0.661682
 Standard dev 0.347698
 Max value 1.08000
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 1526.49
 Standard dev 12.0809
 Max value 1548.88
 Min value 1489.91

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 51.0030
 Standard dev 1.623058e-02
 Max value 51.0305
 Min value 50.9753

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 528
 Mean -3.45954
 Standard dev 0.192235
 Max value -3.12882
 Min value -3.79213

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 528
 Mean -5.52923
 Standard dev 0.606094
 Max value -3.89214
 Min value -6.79025

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 10.9375
 Standard dev 0.277651
 Max value 11.5375
 Min value 9.97136

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 0.234332
 Standard dev 0.409770
 Max value 1.05538
 Min value -0.706833

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 12.2667
 Standard dev 0.415904
 Max value 13.2034
 Min value 11.3902

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 296.818

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 528
 Mean 99.2470
 Standard dev 1.39410
 Max value 102.231
 Min value 94.9569

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 262.490

A531 02-APR-97 P2 FL050-FL150 From 132232-133220 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:25

A531 02-APR-97 P2 FL050-FL150 From 132232-133220 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:25

A531 02-APR-97 P2 FL050-FL150 From 132232-133220 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:06

A531 02-APR-97 P2 FL050-FL150 From 132232-133220 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:06

A531 02-APR-97 R3 FL150 From 132220-135216 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:28

A531 02-APR-97 R3 FL150 From 132220-135216 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:28

A531 02-APR-97 R3 FL150 From 132220-135216 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:13

A531 02-APR-97 R3 FL150 From 132220-135216 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:13

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 614.614
 Standard dev 76.4798
 Max value 841.570
 Min value 570.002

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 262.956
 Standard dev 5.58189
 Max value 278.742
 Min value 259.101

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 246.913
 Standard dev 7.53594
 Max value 269.781
 Min value 236.484

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 52.1294
 Standard dev 5.56713
 Max value 62.2181
 Min value 38.4489

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 13.3740
 Standard dev 0.830431
 Max value 15.4452
 Min value 10.7431

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 0.706155
 Standard dev 1.50952
 Max value 13.8480
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 4065.58
 Standard dev 890.369
 Max value 4596.00
 Min value 1538.50

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 50.9163
 Standard dev 3.379698e-02
 Max value 50.9764
 Min value 50.8544

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean -5.03358
 Standard dev 0.750512
 Max value -3.77668
 Min value -6.33842

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 0.126228
 Standard dev 1.66013
 Max value 3.16335
 Min value -5.48823

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 12.5063
 Standard dev 1.10150
 Max value 15.6259
 Min value 9.69569

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean -0.246355
 Standard dev 1.00455
 Max value 1.51888
 Min value -2.32043

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 12.6183
 Standard dev 1.08213
 Max value 15.6290
 Min value 9.94212

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 269.422

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1797
 Mean 112.914
 Standard dev 4.99913
 Max value 118.723
 Min value 99.8509

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 265.687

A531 02-APR-97 P3 FL150-500' From 135421-141058 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:31

A531 02-APR-97 P3 FL150-500' From 135421-141058 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:31

A531 02-APR-97 P3 FL150-500' From 135421-141058 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:18

A531 02-APR-97 P3 FL150-500' From 135421-141058 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:18

A531 02-APR-97 R4 800'-1100' From 141124-142620 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:33

A531 02-APR-97 R4 800'-1100' From 141124-142620 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:33

A531 02-APR-97 R4 800'-1100' From 141124-142620 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:21

A531 02-APR-97 R4 800'-1100' From 141124-142620 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:22

A531 02-APR-97 R4 800'-1100' From 141124-142620 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:22

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 897
Mean 985.690
Standard dev 6.60530
Max value 995.250
Min value 975.335

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 897
Mean 281.257
Standard dev 0.267924
Max value 281.698
Min value 280.660

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 897
Mean 278.600
Standard dev 0.880164
Max value 279.969
Min value 275.495

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 897
Mean 59.1751
Standard dev 3.01923
Max value 67.8876
Min value 48.3199

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 897
Mean 13.1940
Standard dev 1.29562
Max value 15.4971
Min value 10.4464

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 897
Mean 0.300281
Standard dev 0.114149
Max value 0.480000
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 897
Mean 284.599
Standard dev 55.0546
Max value 372.281
Min value 204.085

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 897
Mean 50.4748
Standard dev 0.224490
Max value 50.8663
Min value 50.0891

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 897
Mean -6.42651
Standard dev 2.180467e-02
Max value -6.38743
Min value -6.45894

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 897
Mean 4.36127
Standard dev 0.976943
Max value 6.83223
Min value 2.57868

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 897
Mean 4.26295
Standard dev 1.15768
Max value 6.79234
Min value 2.68388

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 897
Mean 6.439343e-02
Standard dev 0.300172
Max value 1.31425
Min value -0.771637

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 897
Mean 6.14441
Standard dev 1.31665
Max value 8.95998
Min value 3.85527

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 224.347

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 897
Mean 92.4538
Standard dev 1.58954
Max value 96.1164
Min value 88.0273

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 356.650

A531 02-APR-97 P4 1100'-FL270 From 142711-145338 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:37

A531 02-APR-97 P4 1100'-FL270 From 142711-145338 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:37

A531 02-APR-97 P4 1100'-FL270 From 142711-145338 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:29

A531 02-APR-97 P4 1100'-FL270 From 142711-145338 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:29

A531 02-APR-97 R5 FL270 From 145507-151156 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:40

A531 02-APR-97 R5 FL270 From 145507-151156 Plotted 18-Jan-1997 09:40

A531 02-APR-97 R5 FL270 From 145507-151156 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:34

A531 02-APR-97 R5 FL270 From 145507-151156 Potted 9-Jun-1997 17:34

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 345.926
 Standard dev 0.137269
 Max value 346.228
 Min value 345.441

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 232.770
 Standard dev 0.243994
 Max value 233.189
 Min value 232.278

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 221.323
 Standard dev 0.493029
 Max value 222.057
 Min value 220.201

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 49.7718
 Standard dev 24.7411
 Max value 78.3880
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 12.5524
 Standard dev 0.258113
 Max value 13.0538
 Min value 12.1387

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 0.267216
 Standard dev 1.12000
 Max value 12.6080
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 8197.72
 Standard dev 2.72726
 Max value 8207.37
 Min value 8191.71

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 51.1098
 Standard dev 0.148180
 Max value 51.3624
 Min value 50.8558

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1010
 Mean -4.78670
 Standard dev 0.592917
 Max value -3.76062
 Min value -5.81874

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 1.31196
 Standard dev 0.687038
 Max value 2.55527
 Min value -0.189133

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 15.9365
 Standard dev 0.705935
 Max value 17.9817
 Min value 14.6618

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1010
 Mean -0.118000
 Standard dev 0.407624
 Max value 1.09011
 Min value -0.875977

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 16.0068
 Standard dev 0.668374
 Max value 17.9853
 Min value 14.8069

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 265.294

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1010
 Mean 138.120
 Standard dev 2.48962
 Max value 142.116
 Min value 133.477

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 68.6563

A531 02-APR-97 P5 FL270-FL150 From 151304-152507 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:42

A531 02-APR-97 P5 FL270-FL150 From 151304-152507 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:42

A531 02-APR-97 P5 FL270-FL150 From 151304-152507 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:37

A531 02-APR-97 P5 FL270-FL150 From 151304-152507 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:37

A531 02-APR-97 R6 FL150 From 152507-154150 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:44

A531 02-APR-97 R6 FL150 From 152507-154150 Plotted 18-Jun-1997 09:45

A531 02-APR-97 R6 FL150 From 152507 - 154150 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:41

A531 02-APR-97 R6 FL150 From 152507-154150 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 17:41

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1004
Mean 572.043
Standard dev 0.209547
Max value 573.527
Min value 571.472

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1004
Mean 259.415
Standard dev 0.228950
Max value 259.856
Min value 258.897

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1004
Mean 242.152
Standard dev 3.64481
Max value 252.590
Min value 234.823

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1004
Mean 59.2202
Standard dev 3.36069
Max value 65.7020
Min value 47.5062

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 1004
Mean 11.3866
Standard dev 0.734041
Max value 12.7376
Min value 10.5963

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 1004
Mean 0.179490
Standard dev 0.130757
Max value 0.440000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1004
Mean 4568.97
Standard dev 2.77055
Max value 4576.52
Min value 4549.37

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1004
Mean 51.0925
Standard dev 6.440071e-04
Max value 51.0936
Min value 51.0913

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1004
Mean -3.36029
Standard dev 0.534656
Max value -2.44123
Min value -4.28961

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1004
Mean 2.54426
Standard dev 0.573276
Max value 3.81271
Min value 1.32817

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1004
Mean 14.2769
Standard dev 0.915442
Max value 15.8194
Min value 12.0314

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1004
Mean 0.404352
Standard dev 0.773834
Max value 2.81282
Min value -0.478699

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1004
Mean 14.5148
Standard dev 0.889102
Max value 16.0956
Min value 12.3996

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 259.896

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1004
Mean 114.720
Standard dev 1.43256
Max value 118.152
Min value 111.825

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 90.0185

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument "the fluorescence water vapour sensor".

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm^3) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μm to 3.00 μm , to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μm diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$H_2O_2 = (k_3 j_4 [O_3] [H_2O]) / (k_5 [M] (j_6 + k_7 + [OH] k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + H_2O \rightarrow 2OH$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + M \rightarrow O(^3P) + M$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $OH + H_2O_2 \rightarrow H_2O + HO_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O_3 + h\nu \rightarrow O(^1D) + O_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $H_2O_2 + h\nu \rightarrow OH + OH$

j_4 , j_6 and $[OH]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NOxy:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_{y1}, NO_{y2}) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in volts. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).
- **Bags/CO analysis:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office). Analysis was carried out at ITE Edinburgh by Neil Cape. Plots of CO (ppb) with altitude (pressure height in metres) are included. Contamination has been noted in some of the bag samples, for further advice contact ITE Edinburgh.

ARASF

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